

Fracture mechanics simulations of graphene composites using a 3D meshfreehierarchical model

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ABSTRACT

It is known that an appealing strategy in developing novel composite materials is to reproduce complex structures found in nature, leading to smart and multifunctional solutions with optimized properties [1]. In biologic structural materials, the arrangement of nano- to macro- components is generally organized in a hierarchical structure. Some well-known examples are spider silk, gecko toes, sea shells, bone, etc. These novel structural criteria introduce new possibilities in the field of composite material design, in particular since the introduction of nano-reinforcements such as graphene, opening up the possibility of creating truly multiscale composite materials, which could potentially achieve tailor-made, simultaneously optimized mechanical properties, such as stiffness, strength, toughness, etc. To design such materials, a robust multiscale simulation approach needs to be developed to aid in preparing experimental solutions.

Here, we develop a multiscale numerical model to simulate the mechanisms involved in damage progression and energy dissipation at different size scales in such hierarchical graphene nanocomposites, considering all relevant parameters: depend both on the heterogeneity of the material (defects and reinforcements), hierarchical structure, interface properties between matrix and reinforcements, etc. All of these aspects are incorporated into a 2-D or 3D model, based on a meshfree numerical approach [2], which is able to simulate both damage nucleation and progression. The model is validated by comparing numerical results to continuum mechanics and fracture mechanics theories, and then employed to model experimental data relative to polymer composites with reinforcements at different size scales (e.g. graphene nanoplatelets as well as conventional glass/carbon fibre reinforcements). The agreement between numerical and experimental results shows that the developed code could be a valuable support in the design and optimization of these advanced composite materials, drawing inspiration and going beyond biological materials with exceptional mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mechanical properties displayed by biomaterials often differ and exceed traditional engineering materials in that they display some optimized competing properties such as strength and toughness or stiffness and density [3, 4]. The mechanisms involved in these properties are usually linked to the internal structures of biomaterials, which include complex heterogeneous architectures, with a hierarchical arrangement of microstructural and base components [5, 6].

In order to obtain artificial materials with similar properties, the challenge is therefore to capture the optimization criteria related to the internal structure and replicate them [7, 8]. Fibre-based composites already combine lightweight and directional strengthening elements to optimize the material response to specific applications, but are as yet unable to simultaneously obtain the optimized stiffness/density or strength/toughness combinations found in biocomposites. With the recent introduction of nano reinforcements such as carbon nanotubes, nano ribbons or graphene [9, 10], new possibilities of artificial multiscale hierarchical composites have emerged and the present work could be a valuable support in the design and optimization of these advanced materials, drawing inspiration and going beyond biological materials with exceptional mechanical properties.

Here, we developed a numerical model based on a mesh free method to study the impact of the composite structures on global mechanical properties (figure 1). Classic finite element models encounter difficulties to model crack growth, which is in the present study related to the determination of the composite strength and toughness, and requires complex remeshing procedures. The mesh free approach provides accurate solutions to the description of crack growth problems [2].

Figure 1: Hierarchical organisation of a multiscale composite material.

2. NUMERICAL MODEL

To capture the strength, stiffness and toughness properties of composite structures, we use a numerical model based on mesh free method. This approach allows to simulate large deformations, when necessary nonlinear behaviour and crack propagation avoiding degeneration and singularities that can arise using classical finite elements. The method is based on the so-called “element free Galerkin” (EFG) approach. The method employs moving least squares approximations of the shape functions.

Considering an elastic problem, with no body forces, the equilibrium of the domain Ω (shown in figure 2) is:

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = 0 & x \in \Omega \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \bar{\mathbf{t}} & x \in \Gamma_t \\ u = \bar{u} & x \in \Gamma_u \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor, \mathbf{n} is the normal unity vector on the boundary Γ_t with a prescribed traction $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$, and \bar{u} the prescribed displacement on the essential boundary Γ_u .

Using the displacement \mathbf{u} as trial function:

$$u(x) = \sum_{I=1}^n \phi_I d_I \quad (2)$$

Where n is the number of nodes, ϕ_I the shape function and d_I the nodal parameter vector. The weak form of the problem becomes:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \epsilon^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_t} \delta u^T \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma_t + \int_{\Gamma_u} \delta \lambda^T (u - \bar{u}) d\Gamma_u + \int_{\Gamma_u} \delta u^T \lambda d\Gamma_u = 0 \quad (3)$$

using Lagrange multipliers λ for the enforced boundary conditions.

The fracture criterion for crack growth depends on the stress field in the neighbourhood of the crack path. The domain of influence, e.g. the support of the shape functions near the crack is modified to account for the discontinuity in the material (as shown in figure 2).

Stiff inclusions are added in the matrix to model the composite structure. Depending on the dimensions ratios of the reinforcement, they can be modelled as a subdomain with different mechanical properties, or as rigid sub elements implemented as a boundary condition.

To simulate multiple scale levels, i.e. the hierarchical organisation of the composite, we apply a bottom up strategy. From the nano or micro scale, we derive mechanical properties and global material response to various loading cases and use them as input for the upper scale level. If random structures are added at the lower hierarchy level, the mechanical properties are defined in the upper level by a Weibull probability law, by calculating scale and shape parameters from the obtained distribution.

Figure 2: Schematic of the numerical approach.

3. SIMULATIONS

When deriving the upper scale material properties from the lower scale, the first step is to define the mechanical properties as a function of the reinforcement shape, size and orientation (figure 3, 4b) at the lowest scale (nanotubes or graphene embedded in the matrix). It is well known [12] that the presence of stiff inclusions gives on the one hand a stiffening of the material, but on the other hand, generates a stress concentration inside the material, which leads to a decrease in toughness. Matrix properties also play an important role here, including non-local or non-linear effects that play a role in redistributing the load around the most stressed domains and delaying crack nucleation.

Figure 3: A) Orientation of the reinforcements inside the matrix, B) overlapping in the composite structure.

At a single scale level, an optimisation criterion is derived as a function of the geometry of the inclusions. Some organized structures with preferential orientation and/or overlapping of the reinforcements are likely to give different results with respect to a fully random configuration. As a simple example, oriented line inclusions (such as nanotubes) will increase the stiffness of the composite in the direction of the line, whereas the stiffness in the other directions will remain virtually unchanged with respect to the matrix stiffness. The challenge is then to create a structure at the upper scale level where the load transfer between the reinforcements through the matrix take advantage of the lower scale optimized properties.

Figure 4: A) Strain field calculated with the meshfree model of a cracked specimen undergoing uniaxial tension. B) Stress field in presence of a fiber reinforcement under uniaxial tension.

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